

Effect of Chemical Reaction Heat Mass Transfer of Carbon Nanotubes in A Vertical Channel Filled With Casson Fluid

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Abstract

This paper presents the analytical investigation of Poiseuille flow on heat mass transfer of Single Wall Carbon Nanotubes (SWCNTs) and Multiple Wall Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNTs) for mixed convection along a vertical channel filled with Casson fluid. This Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) are suspended in three different types of base fluid (Water, Kerosene and engine oil). Xue model has been used for effective thermal conductivity of CNTs. The resultant equations are solved for velocity, temperature and concentration utilizing perturbation method. Expressions for Skin friction, Nusselt number and Sherwood number are also evaluated. Effects of some parameters such as Mass transfer specie which occurs in many processes such as evaporating, cooling, sublimation, condensation and drying. It is spotted that increasing in volume fraction (ϕ), leads to decreases in the velocity and Skin friction profiles of the fluid, because the nanofluid becomes more viscous due to adding carbon nanotubes. Maximizing values of chemical reaction, lead to increases in rate of heat transfer in carbon nanotubes.

Keywords: Fluid, flow, MHD, Nanotubes, Casson fluid, Chemical reaction.

1. Introduction

The study of Casson fluid has attracted attention to many researchers due to its application in the field of metallurgy, food processing, drilling operations, and bioengineering operations. Its application extends to the manufacturing of pharmaceutical products, coal in water, china clay, paints, synthetic lubricants, and biological fluids such as synovial fluids, sewage sludge, jelly, tomato sauce, honey, soup, and blood due to its contents such as plasma, fibrinogen, and protein, making the study of Casson fluid important in fluid dynamics. Casson fluid is classified as a non-Newtonian fluid due to its rheological characteristics. These characteristic show shear stress strain relationships that are significantly different from Newtonian fluids Makanda et al. (2015). Casson fluid is a non-Newtonian fluid that was first introduced by Casson in 1959. It exhibits a yield stress. If a shear stress less than the yield stress is applied to the fluid, it behaves or acts like a solid, where if a shear stress greater than the yield stress is applied, it starts to move. Some example of Casson fluid are Jelly, honey, tomato sauce, human blood, chocolate, shampoo, etc. (Casson,1959). The nonlinear Casson's constitutive equation has been found to describe accurately the flow curves of suspensions of pigments in the lithographic vanishes used for the preparation of printing inks and silicon suspensions. Casson fluid is a class of non-Newtonian fluid which has definite advantage across the other non-Newtonian fluid model. Non-Newtonian fluid has wide application in

petroleum drilling, polymer engineering, manufacturing of food and cosmetics, etc. Dash *et al.* (1996) studied the effect of yield stress on the flow of a Casson fluid in a homogeneous porous medium bounded by a circular cylinder. Pramanic (2014) studied the impact of thermal radiation on the Casson fluid flow and heat transfer through an exponentially inspected porous stretching surface. Asma *et al.* (2015) examined the unsteady magneto hydrodynamic (MHD) flow of Casson fluid through an oscillating plate embedded in a porous medium. Walicka and Falicka (2015) investigated the influence of Reynolds number on the stream of Casson fluid. Nadeem *et al.* (2014) investigated MHD three- dimensional boundary layer flow of Casson fluid with convective boundary condition. Terminology with respect to Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) was first discovered by a Japanese electron microscopist, Lijima (1991) who explored Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNTs) using the Kratschmer and Huffman technique. Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes (SWCNTs) were reported by Ajayan and Lijima (1993). Carbon Nanotubes is a tube shaped material, made of carbon having a diameter measuring on the nanometer scale ranges from 1 to 100nm and length in micrometers. (CNTs) are made of nanoparticles used in nanofluid. They have 200 times strength and 5 times elasticity of steel, 15 times thermal conductivity and 1000 times current capacity of copper, and it also endorsed by environmental protection agency as nonhazardous particle for the environment. Their unique composition, geometry and properties enable numerous potential applications such as energy storage, molecular electronics, thermal materials, fabric and fiber, catalyst supports, Biomedical, air and water filtration, conductive plastics, conductive adhesive, ceramics, etc. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are fullerene-related structures that consist of either a grapheme cylinder the so- called single walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) or a number of concentric cylinders the so-called multiple walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). Much attention has been given to this new type of composite materials because of their novel properties and behaviors that make them useful in wide variety of applications in heat transfer, mass transfer, optics solar collection and other material sciences. Examples of SWCNTs and MWCNTs include pure SWCNT, ultra-pure SWCNT, semi conducting SWCNT, metallic SWCNT, C-grade MWCNT, M-grade MWCNT, X-long MWCNT, Nitrogen doped MWCNT, and Boron doped MWCNT. Lijima (1991) examined helical microtubules of graphite carbon. Wen and Ding (2004) investigated the effect of concentration of CNTs and temperature on effective thermal conductivity. It was found that effective thermal conductivity increased with increasing concentration of CNTs. Marquis and Chibnate (2005) investigated that both SWCNT and MWCNTs increased the thermal conductivity of nano fluid and nano lubricants, they used three different types of nano fluids and nano lubricants in their study. Khan *et al.* (2014) studied fluid flow and heat transfer of CNTs along a flat plate with Navier slip boundary condition. Manevitch *et al.* (2017) studied nonlinear optical vibration of single walled carbon nanotubes. Expressions with respect to nano fluids were initially presented by Choi (1995) using the inconsistent thermal conductivity of liquid (water) by depositing copper nanomaterial. Said *et al.* (2014) reported that the SWCNT nano-liquids improve the thermal performance of solar collectors in place of water, in a context where one of the most manageable and contamination-free source of renewable energy is solar energy, and solar aerals. It can transform solar radiation into heat

energy. In the textile industry, much attention has been paid to coating CNTs because of their uses in the sound industry, for example in megaphones and headsets. Xiao et al. (2015) reported that very thin CNT films radiate lurid sound, and therefore prepared thin film CNT megaphones. Halefadi et al. (2014) examined the productivity of water-based nanofluid CNTs and deliberated the consequences of stumpy volume fraction nanoparticles in a range from 0.0055% to 0.278% on the physical properties (density, viscosity, thermal conductivity, and specific heat) of nanofluids. Aman et al. (2017) investigated the influence of magneto hydro dynamics on Poiseuille flow and heat analysis of CNTs with a Casson fluid vertical channel. Muhammad et al. (2018) studied the rotating flow of magneto hydrodynamic Carbon Nanotubes over a stretching sheet with the impact of non-Linear thermal radiation and heat generation/absorption. Simultaneous heat and mass transfer occurs in power industries, in many chemical engineering processes such as drying, evaporation, condensation, sublimation and so on, due to the buoyancy forces arise from both temperature and concentration variation in the fluid. When heat and mass transfer occur simultaneously in a moving fluid affecting each other causes a cross diffusion effect, the mass transfer caused by temperature gradient is called the Soret effect, while the heat transfer caused by concentration effect is called the Dufour effect. Soret and Dufour effects are important phenomena in areas such as hydrology, petrology, and geosciences. The Soret effect, for instance, has been utilized for isotope separation and in a mixture between gases with very light molecular weight (He , H_2) and of medium molecular weight (N_2 , air). The Dufour effect was recently found to be of order of considerable magnitude so that it cannot be neglected, Eckert and Drake (1974). Many researchers studied Soret and Dufour effects, for example, Postelnica (2010) analyzed the effect of Soret and Dufour on heat and mass transfer. Chamkha and El-Kabeir (2013) presented a theoretical study of Soret and Dufour effects on unsteady coupled heat and mass transfer by mixed convection flow over a vertical cone rotating in an ambient fluid in the presence of a magnetic field and chemical reaction. Usman and Uwanta (2013) have considered the effect of thermal conductivity on MHD heat and mass transfer flow past an infinite vertical plate with Soret and Dufour effects. Mixed convection flow in a channel has gained much attention such as in thermal and nuclear power engineering. Mixed convection together with Pulsatile Poiseuille flow (PPF) or simply mixed convection PPF is of great importance. In channel flow mixed convection arises due to cooling/ heating the walls of the channel. Makinde and Mhone (2005) analyzed mixed convection flow with combined effect of a transverse magnetic field and radiative heat transfer of optically thin fluid passing through a channel filled with saturated porous medium and with heated bounding walls. AL- Salem et al. (2012) depicted the influence of moving lid direction on MHD mixed convection in a linearly heated cavity. They concluded that in case of mixed convection, the direction of lid is more effective than in case of forced convection. Salleh et al. (2010) analyzed numerically mixed convection flow of a solid sphere. Aaiza et al. (2015) studied mixed convection flow of nanofluid for different shapes of nanoparticles in a channel. They found that Grashof number leads to an increase in buoyancy force and hence fluid flow increases.

The present study will enhance the understanding of the effect of chemical reaction heat mass transfer of Carbon Nanotubes in a vertical channel filled with Casson Fluid as applied in various engineering processes.

2. Formulation and Solution of the Problem

Consider MHD flow in a vertical channel of width d , with static walls at $y = 0$, and $y = d$, with heat mass transfer in a Casson fluid (three different fluids i.e. Water, Engine oil and Kerosene based nano fluids) containing SWCNTs and MWCNTs. The flow is assumed to be incompressible and unsteady. A uniform magnetic field of strength B_0 is applied in a perpendicular direction to the flow (along x axis). Mixed convection is generated by external pressure gradient together with buoyancy force. The viscous dissipation effect is neglected in the energy equation. In vertical channel T_0 and T_d show the plate temperatures. The concentration of the fluid from the plate are C_0 and C_d , respectively. The Reynolds number is assumed small. From Bossiness approximation assumption the governing equations of momentum, heat and mass transfer are:

Momentum Equation

$$\rho_{nf} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \mu_{nf} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \sigma_{nf} \beta_0^2 U + (\rho\beta_T)_{nf} g(T - T_d) + (\rho\beta_C)_{nf} g(C - C_d) \quad (2.1)$$

Heat Transfer Equation

$$(\rho C_p)_{nf} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = K_{nf} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} \quad (2.2)$$

Mass Transfer Equation

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D_{nf} \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} - K^*(C - C_d) \quad (2.3)$$

With corresponding boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} U(0, t) &= 0; \quad U(d, t) = 0 \\ T(0, t) &= T_0; \quad T(d, t) = T_d \\ C(0, t) &= C_0; \quad T(d, t) = C_d \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

Figure 2.1: Schematic diagram of the flow

There are many theoretical models in the literature which can predict the thermal conductivities of CNTs such as Maxwell, Jeffery, Davis, Hamilton and crosser model. Xue (2005) perceived that the prevailing models are only authentic for spherical or elliptical particles with minor axial ratio. Another, limitation of those models is that they do not deem for the impact of space distribution of CNTs on thermal conductivity. As in the following, Xue (2005) model is used in these problems for thermal conductivity and dynamic viscosity of CNTs.

$$\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} = \frac{1-\phi+2\phi\left(\frac{k_{CNT}}{k_{CNT}-k_f}\right)\ln\frac{k_{CNT}+k_f}{2k_f}}{1-\phi+2\phi\left(\frac{k_f}{k_{CNT}-k_f}\right)\ln\frac{k_{CNT}+k_f}{2k_f}} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\mu_{nf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1-\phi)^{2.5}} \quad (2.6)$$

The density ρ_{nf} , thermal expansion coefficient $(\rho\beta)_{nf}$, heat capacitance $(\rho c_p)_{nf}$, thermal conductivity σ_{nf} , is derived by using the relations given by Mustapha and Junaid, (2015) and Hussain et al. (2016).

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{nf} &= (1-\phi)\rho_f + \phi\rho_{CNT}, \\ (\rho\beta)_{nf} &= (1-\phi)(\rho\beta)_f + \phi(\rho\beta)_{CNT}, \\ (\rho c)_{nf} &= (1-\phi)(\rho c_p)_f + \phi(\rho c_p)_{CNT} \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

The external pressure gradient in the flow direction is taken as $-\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = \lambda \varepsilon e^{(i\omega t)}$.

The radiation heat flux is given by
$$\frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} = -4\alpha^2(T - T_d) \quad (2.8)$$

Introducing the following dimensionless quantities

$$\begin{aligned} x^* &= \frac{x}{d}, y^* = \frac{y}{d}, u^* = \frac{u}{U_o}, t^* = \frac{tU_o}{d}, p^* = \frac{d}{\mu U_o} p, T^* = \frac{T-T_d}{T_o-T_d}, \\ \omega^* &= \frac{d\omega}{U_o}, -\frac{\partial p^*}{\partial x^*} = \lambda \varepsilon e^{(i\omega t)}, C^* = \frac{C-C_d}{C_o-C_d} \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

Substituting equation (2.8) in to equation (2.2) yields

$$(\rho C_p)_{nf} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = K_{nf} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + 4\alpha^2(T - T_d) \quad (2.10)$$

Using the non-dimensional variables (2.9) in to equations [(2.1)-(2.8) and (2.10)] and in view of the above relations, we get (the * symbol is dropped out for the sake of Simplicity).

$$a_o \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} - a_1 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + a_2 u = \lambda \varepsilon e^{i\omega t} + a_3 T + a_4 C \quad (2.11)$$

$$b_o^2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + b_1^2 T \quad (2.12)$$

$$b_{17}^2 \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} - b_{18}^2 C \quad (2.13)$$

Corresponding boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} u(0,t) &= 0, & u(d,t) &= 0 \\ T(0,t) &= 1, & T(d,t) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

$$C(0,t) = 1, \quad C(d,t) = 0$$

In order to solve equations (2.11) to (2.13) subject to boundary conditions (2.14), the following perturbed solutions for velocity, temperature and concentration are considered:

$$u(y,t) = u_o(y) + \varepsilon e^{i\omega t} u_1(y) \quad (2.15)$$

$$T(y,t) = T_o(y) + \varepsilon e^{i\omega t} T_1(y) \quad (2.16)$$

$$C(y,t) = C_o(y) + \varepsilon e^{i\omega t} C_1(y) \quad (2.17)$$

Where $u_o(y), u_1(y), T_o(y), T_1(y), C_o(y)$ and $C_1(y)$ are to be determined.

Using equations (2.15) to (2.17) in to the equations (2.11) to (2.14), the following Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) are obtained.

$$u_o'' - a_5^2 u_o = -\frac{a_3}{a_1} T_o - \frac{a_4}{a_1} C_o \quad (2.18)$$

$$u_1'' - a_6^2 u_1 = -\frac{\lambda}{a_1} - \frac{a_3}{a_1} T_1 - \frac{a_4}{a_1} C_1 \quad (2.19)$$

$$T_o'' + b_1^2 T_o = 0 \quad (2.20)$$

$$T_1'' + b_2^2 T_1 = 0 \quad (2.21)$$

$$C_o'' - b_{18}^2 C_o = 0 \quad (2.22)$$

$$C_1'' - b_{19}^2 C_1 = 0 \quad (2.23)$$

with corresponding boundary conditions as follows;

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_o(o) = o, u_o(1) = o, u_1(0) = o, u_1(1) = o, \\
 T_o(0) = 1, T_o(1) = 0, T_1(0) = 0, T_1(1) = 0, \\
 C_o(0) = 1, C_o(1) = 0, C_1(0) = 0, C_1(1) = 0,
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.24}$$

Solving the system equations (2.18) to (2.23) subject to boundary conditions (2.24), we obtained

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_o(y) = \frac{a_3}{a_1(b_1^2 + a_5^2)} \left[\frac{\sin b_1(1-y)}{\sin(b_1)} - \frac{\sinh a_5(1-y)}{\sinh(a_5)} \right] \\
 + \frac{a_4}{a_1(b_{18}^2 - a_5^2)} \left[\frac{\sinh a_5(1-y)}{\sinh(a_5)} - \frac{\sinh b_{18}(1-y)}{\sinh(b_{18})} \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.25}$$

$$u_1(y) = \frac{\lambda}{a_1 a_6^2} \left[\frac{\sinh a_6(y-1) - \sinh(a_6 y)}{\sinh(a_6)} + 1 \right] \tag{2.26}$$

$$T_o(y) = \frac{\sin b_1(1-y)}{\sin(b_1)} \tag{2.27}$$

$$T_1(y) = 0 \tag{2.28}$$

$$C_o(y) = \frac{\sinh b_{18}(1-y)}{\sinh(b_{18})} \tag{2.29}$$

$$C_1(y) = o \tag{2.30}$$

In view of the above solutions, the velocity, temperature and concentration distributions become;

$$\begin{aligned}
 u(y,t) = \frac{a_3}{a_1[b_1^2 + a_5^2]} \left[\frac{\sin b_1(1-y)}{\sin(b_1)} - \frac{\sinh a_5(1-y)}{\sinh(a_5)} \right] + \frac{a_4}{a_1[b_{18}^2 - a_5^2]} \left[\frac{\sinh a_5(1-y)}{\sinh(a_5)} - \frac{\sinh b_{18}(1-y)}{\sinh(b_{18})} \right] \\
 + \varepsilon e^{i\omega t} \left[\frac{\lambda}{a_1 a_6^2} \left(\frac{\sinh a_6(y-1) - \sinh(a_6 y)}{\sinh(a_6)} + 1 \right) \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.31}$$

$$T(y,t) = \frac{\sin b_1(1-y)}{\sin(b_1)} \quad (2.32)$$

$$C(y,t) = \frac{\sinh b_{18}(1-y)}{\sinh(b_{18})} \quad (2.33)$$

The Skin friction, heat transfer rate and mass transfer rate are evaluated from equations (2.31) to (2.33) when differentiated at $y = 0$ as follows:

$$C_f = \frac{a_3}{a_1 [b_1^2 + a_5^2]} \left[\frac{a_5 \cosh a_5}{\sinh a_5} - \frac{b_1 \cos b_1}{\sin b_1} \right] + \frac{a_4}{a_1 [b_{18}^2 - a_5^2]} \left[\frac{b_{18} \cosh b_{18}}{\sinh b_{18}} - \frac{a_5 \cosh a_5}{\sinh a_5} \right] + \varepsilon e^{i\omega t} \left[\frac{\lambda}{a_1 a_6^2} \left(-\frac{a_6 \cosh a_6 - a_6}{\sinh a_6} \right) \right] \quad (2.34)$$

$$Nu = -\frac{b_1 \cos b_1}{\sin b_1} \quad (2.35)$$

$$S_h = -\frac{b_{18} \cosh b_{18}}{\sinh b_{18}} \quad (2.36)$$

3. Results and Discussion

Heat and mass transfer mixed convection Poiseuille flow of carbon nanotubes with Casson fluid inside a vertical channel is analyzed with chemical reaction parameter. Both the flow and heat mass transfer analysis of single and multiple walls carbon nanotubes suspended in three different types of based fluids (water, kerosene and engine oil) were considered. The analytical solution for governing partial differential equations with their boundary conditions in non-dimensional form are computed using two term perturbation techniques on the basis of Xue model (2005). Figure 2.1 shows the schematic flow geometry of the problem. Thermo physical properties of based fluids and CNTs are given in table 3.1. Thermal conductivity values of CNTs with different values of volume fraction are given in table 3.2. The effects of values in this paper such as Schmidt number ($Sc = 0.6$), Casson parameter ($\beta = 0.5$), Reynolds number ($Re = 0.1$), magnetic parameter ($M = 0.01$), thermal Grashof number ($Gr = 1.5$), mass Grashof number ($Gc = 1.5$), Prandtl number ($Pr = 7$) corresponding to water, radiation parameter ($N = 1.6$), nano particles volume fraction ($\phi = 0.02$), time ($t = 1$), chemical reaction ($\gamma = 0.05$), oscillation frequency ($\omega = 1$), epsilon ($\varepsilon = 0.0001$), are illustrated in the graphs. All graphs therefore correspond to these unless specifically indicated on the appropriate graph.

Figure 3.0: Single and Multiple Walls Carbon Nanotubes.

Table 3.1. Thermo physical properties of base fluids and carbon nanotubes (Aman et al. 2017)

Base fluids and Nanoparticles	Density $\rho(kg / m^3)$	Specific heat Capacity $C_p(kg^{-1} / k^{-1})$	Thermal conductivity $k(Wm^{-1}k^{-1})$	$(\beta \times 10^{-5} k^{-1})$
Water	997	4179	0.613	21
Kerosene oil	783	2090	0.145	99
Engine oil	884	1910	0.144	70
SWCNT	2600	425	6600	27
MWCNT	1600	796	3000	44

Table 3.2. Thermal conductivity values of CNTs with different values of volume fraction.

Volume fraction ϕ	Thermal conductivity k_{nf} for SWCNT	Thermal conductivity k_{nf} for MWCNT
0	0.145	0.145
0.01	0.174	0.172
0.02	0.204	0.2
0.03	0.235	0.228
0.04	0.266	0.257

Temperature Profiles

Figure 3.1: Temperature profile for various values of ϕ and N in water-based nano fluid for SWCNT and MWCNT.

Figure 3.2: Temperature profile for various values of ϕ and N in kerosene oil-based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT.

Figure 3.3: Temperature profile for various values of ϕ and N in engine oil-based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT

Figures 3.1 to 3.3 are depicted to examine the effect of radiation parameter N with volume fraction ϕ on nanofluid temperature. It is observed that sinusoidal effect maximizes with increase in radiation parameter N , in both the three different based fluid and also identical pattern is observed for both SWCNT and MWCNT for the same values of volume fraction ϕ

Concentration Profiles

Figure 3.4: Concentration profile for various values of γ and N in Water-based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT.

Figure 3.5: Concentration profile for various values of γ and N in kerosene oil-based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT.

Figure 3.6: Concentration profile for various values of γ and N in engine oil-based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT.

Figure 3.7: Concentration profile for various values of ϕ and Sc in Water-based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT when $\phi = 0.00, 1.04$.

Figure 3.8: Concentration profile for various values of ϕ and Sc in kerosene oil-based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT when $\phi = 0.00, 1.04$.

Figure 3.9: Concentration profile for various values of ϕ and Sc in engine oil-based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT when $\phi = 0.00, 1.04$.

Figures 3.4 to 3.6 depicts that the concentration decreases with increasing the values of γ , in all the three different based nanofluid. The production of energy during chemical reaction causes this fall in concentration profile. The influence of Schmidt number (Sc) on the concentration is illustrated graphically in figures 3.7 to 3.9. The concentration decreases as the Schmidt number (Sc) increases. The concentration boundary layer thickness decreases with increasing values of (Sc), in practice, increasing (Sc) means increasing momentum diffusion over mass diffusion which in turn reduces the concentration profile.

Velocity Profiles

Figure 3.10: Velocity profile for various values of β and M in water -based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT.

Figure 3.11: Velocity profile for various values of β and M in kerosene oil -based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT.

Figure 3.12: Velocity profile for various values of β and M in engine oil -based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT

In figures 3.10 to 3.12 illustrates the behaviors of Casson parameter β and magnetic parameter M simultaneously on velocity profile for SWCNT and MWCNT. Velocity of the fluid increases with increasing values of β . Also, similar pattern is observed for both SWCNT and MWCNT in all the three different based fluids. In practice, increasing β results is an increase in the plastic dynamic viscosity that produces a resistance between the fluid layers hence decreases the flow. It is obvious from the sketch that an increment in the values of M depreciates the value of velocity profile. Usually, high value of M improves the contradictory force known as Lorentz force. Here the influence of β signify a decrease in yield stress of the Casson parameter, this assists the fluid motion and hence accelerates the flow.

Figure 3.13: Velocity profile for various values of ϕ and N in water -based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT

Figure 3.14: Velocity profile for various values of ϕ and N in kerosene oil -based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT.

Figure 3.15: Velocity profile for various values of ϕ and N in engine oil -based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT

In figures 3.13 to 15 depicts the effects of N and ϕ on velocity profile. Velocity decreases with increasing values of ϕ because the fluid becomes more viscous due to the adding SWCNT and MWCNT. Velocity exhibits decrease by increasing N .

Figure 3.16: Velocity profile for various values of γ and Gr in water -based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT.

Figure 3.17: Velocity profile for various values of γ and Gr in kerosene oil -based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT

Figure 3.18: Velocity profile for various values of γ and Gr in engine oil -based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT

Figures 3.16 to 3.18 depicts velocity profile increases simultaneously with increasing values of Gr and γ . Gr signifies the relative effects of the thermal buoyancy force to the viscous hydrodynamics force. The flow is raised to the enhancement in buoyancy force corresponding to increases in the Gr . It is observed that Gr influences the velocity field almost in the boundary layer when compared to far away from the plate. Velocity boundary layer decreases with increasing values of γ .

Skin Friction Profiles

Figure 3.19: Skin friction against magnetic field parameter (M) for various values of ϕ in both the three different based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT

In Figure 3.19, an increase in volume fraction ϕ leads to decrease in skin friction in both CNTs. The graphs indicated that, water have the highest skin friction followed by engine oil then kerosene due to highest density of water compared to engine oil and kerosene oil as given in table 3.1.

Nusselt Number Profiles

Figure 3.20: Nusselt number (Nu) against radiation parameter (N) for various values of ϕ in both the three different based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT

Sherwood Number Profiles

Figure 3.21: Sherwood number (Sh) against Schmidt number (Sc) for various values of γ in both the three different based nanofluid for SWCNT and MWCNT

Figure 3.20 all the three different base fluids have collides to each other due to increases in values of ϕ for both SWCNT and MWCNT. Sherwood number profile has no significant difference between all the three types of based fluids. In Figure 3.21, an increase in chemical reaction γ leads to decrease in Sherwood number. The graph signifies that water, kerosene and engine oil collides to each other for both SWCNT and MWCNT.

4. Conclusions

The chemical reaction effect on natural convection heat and mass transfer of carbon nanotubes inside vertical channel filled with Casson fluid was investigated analytically using Perturbation method. The expressions for velocity, temperature, concentration, skin friction, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number are obtained. The outcomes from the result show that:

- i. The temperature has sinusoidal effect due to increase in radiation parameter (N) and volume fraction (ϕ) in the three based fluid for both SWCNT and MWCNT.
- ii. The velocity increases with increase in Grashof number (Gr), radiation parameter (N), volume fraction (ϕ), and Casson parameter (β) while decreases with chemical reaction parameter (γ), Schmidt number (Sc) and Magnetic parameter (M) in the three based fluid for both SWCNT and MWCNT.
- iii. The increase of volume fraction (ϕ) and chemical reaction parameter (γ), decreases Skin friction and Sherwood numbers respectively.

It is presumed that, with the help of our present model, the physics of flow in a vertical channel filled with Casson fluid can be utilized as a basis for many scientific and engineering applications. The study finds applications in manufacturing of pharmaceutical products, biological fluids and blood due to its contents in plasma study.

Appendix

$$\text{where } \phi_1 = (1 - \phi) + \frac{\phi \rho_{CNT}}{\rho_f}, \phi_2 = \frac{1}{(1 - \phi)^{2.5}}, \phi_3 = \left(1 + \frac{3(\sigma - 1)\phi}{(\sigma + 2) - (\sigma - 1)\phi} \right),$$

$$\phi_4 = (1 - \phi) + \frac{\phi(\rho\beta_T)_{CNT}}{(\rho\beta_T)_f}, \phi_5 = (1 - \phi) + \phi \frac{(\rho c_p)_s}{(\rho c_p)_f}, \phi_6 = (1 - \phi) + \frac{\phi(\rho\beta_C)_{CNT}}{(\rho\beta_C)_f},$$

$$a_o = \phi_1 Re, a_1 = \phi_2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right), a_2 = \phi_3 M, a_3 = Re Gr \phi_4, a_4 = Re Gr \phi_6, a_5^2 = \frac{a_2}{a_1}, a_6^2 = \frac{a_o i \omega + a_2}{a_1},$$

$$b_o^2 = \frac{\phi_5 Pe}{\lambda_{nf}}, b_1^2 = \frac{N^2}{\lambda_{nf}}, b_2^2 = b_1^2 - b_o^2 i \omega, b_3^2 = \frac{\lambda_1^2}{\lambda_{nf}}, b_4^2 = b_2^2, b_5^2 = \frac{b_{18}^2}{\sinh(b_{18})}, b_6^2 = -\frac{a_3}{a_1},$$

$$b_7^2 = \frac{b_3^2 b_5^2 \sinh b_{18}}{(b_{18}^2 + b_1^2) \sin(b_1)}, b_8^2 = \frac{b_3^2 b_5^2}{(b_{18}^2 + b_1^2)}, b_9^2 = \frac{1}{\sin(b_1)}, b_{10}^2 = \frac{a_4}{a_1 \sinh b_{18}} \quad pr = \frac{(\rho c_p)_{f\phi}}{k_f}$$

$$b_{11}^2 = \frac{1}{\sinh\left(\frac{\lambda_2 + \sqrt{\lambda_2^2 - 4b_1^2}}{2}\right)}, b_{12} = \frac{\lambda_2 + \sqrt{\lambda_2^2 - 4b_1^2}}{2}, b_{13}^2 = -\frac{a_4}{a_1 \sinh(b_{14})}, b_{14} = \frac{b_{20}^2 + \sqrt{(b_{20}^2)^2 + 4b_{18}^2}}{2},$$

$$b_{15} = \frac{a_7^2 + \sqrt{(a_7^2)^2 + 4a_5^2}}{2}, b_{16} = \frac{a_7^2 + \sqrt{(a_7^2)^2 + 4a_6^2}}{2}, b_{17}^2 = \frac{Re Sc}{(1-\phi)}, b_{18}^2 = \frac{Re \gamma Sc}{(1-\phi)},$$

$$Gc = \frac{gd(\beta C)_f (C_o - C_d)}{U_o^2}, Gr = \frac{gd(\beta T)_f (T_o - T_d)}{U_o^2}, M = \delta\beta_o^2 \frac{d^2}{\mu_f}, N^2 = \frac{4\alpha^2 d^2}{k_f}, Pe = \frac{U_o d (\rho c_p)_f}{K_f},$$

$$Re = \frac{U_o d \rho}{\mu_f}, Ri = \frac{(\rho c_p)_f U_o d}{K_f}, Sc = \frac{D_f}{dU_o}, \gamma = \frac{dK^*}{U_o}, \lambda_{nf} = \frac{K_{nf}}{K_f}$$

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